

Indirect Spectrophotometric Method for Determination of Vanadium in High Speed Steel

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Manuscript received 7 November 1979, accepted 20 December 1979

An indirect spectrophotometric method for the determination of vanadium based on reduction of Fe(III) to Fe(II) by V(IV), and subsequent formation of ferrous-2,2'-dipyridyl complex was developed. The method was sensitive and was found suitable for determination of vanadium in ores and alloys.

SEVERAL methods¹⁻⁵ have been reported for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium. Some of these methods, though fairly sensitive and useful, are not entirely adequate because of lack of their selectivity. Direct determination of vanadium in presence of common interfering ions is thus unsatisfactory. Benzophenyl hydroxylamine(BPHA) has been reported^{6,7} to be highly specific for vanadium and has been used for its separation and spectrophotometric determination. However, the extractive spectrophotometric method for determination of vanadium using BPHA appears to be less sensitive because of low molar absorptivity of the BPHA complex.

It has been well established⁸⁻¹⁰ that vanadium(IV) is a strong reductant and is oxidised in acid solution at room temperature by iron(III) quantitatively. Furthermore, it is known that vanadium(V) is quantitatively reduced to vanadium(IV) on heating with concentrated HCL.

Based on these facts West and Conrod¹¹ developed an indirect spot test method for detection of vanadium which was subsequently used for the indirect colorimetric^{12,13} and also spectrophotometric¹⁴ determination of vanadium using 2,2'-dipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline respectively. On the basis of the aforesaid principle, we investigated the possibility of using 2,2'-dipyridyl in the indirect spectrophotometric determination of vanadium. A satisfactory method was thus evolved which could find useful application in the determination of vanadium in ores and alloys.

Experimental

Apparatus : Absorbance measurements were made with a Beckman DK-2 Spectrophotometer.

Reagents : Aqueous solutions of the following reagents, prepared in distilled water, were used during the course of investigation. 2,2'-dipyridyl : A 0.2% solution of A. R. 2,2'-dipyridyl. Sodium nitrite : A 10% solution of B.D.H. grade sodium nitrite. Ferric chloride : A 0.1% solution of B.D.H. grade ferric chloride. Sodium phosphate : A 10% solution of A.R. sodium phosphate. Ammonia solution : A dilute solution of ammonia was prepared from liquor ammonia by diluting it in the proportion 1 : 2 with distilled water.

Standard Solution : A. R. ammonium metavanadate was used for preparing a standard stock solution. A 0.01M solution prepared initially in distilled water was used in the experiment after appropriate dilution.

Besides, a number of solutions of other metal ions were prepared to study their effect in the determination of vanadium, and the compounds used for the purpose of preparing these solutions were : CaCO₃, MgCO₃, CuSO₄.5H₂O, ZnSO₄.7H₂O, MnSO₄.5H₂O, Ni(NH₄)₂(SO₄)₂.6H₂O, Pb(NO₃)₂, Fe(NH₄)(SO₄)₂.12H₂O, CdSO₄, PdCl₂, K₂-(PtCl₆), Na₂MoO₄, Na₂WO₄, Cr₂(SO₄)₃, H₂C₂O₄, tartaric acid and citric acid.

Procedure for Calibration : To different aliquots of a standard solution containing 15 to 120 micro gram of vanadium, 0.5 ml of concentrated HCl and 2 ml of 10% sodium nitrite solutions were added and the resulting solutions were allowed to stand for 10 minutes. Each of these solutions was then shaken with 0.5 gram of urea and was allowed to stand with occasional shaking for another 15 minutes. pH of these solutions were then adjusted between 5 and 6 by adding the required quantity of diluted ammonia solution (the amount of ammonia solution required was determined previously by titration of one of the above solutions to the methyl orange end point, subsequent pH measurement on which showed a pH slightly greater than 5). To

these solutions were then added 2 ml of 0.1% FeCl_3 solution followed by addition of 5 ml of 0.2% 2,2'-dipyridyl reagent and 1 ml of 10% sodium phosphate solution. Finally, the volume in each was made up to 25 ml in standard flasks and absorbance was measured at 520 nm after allowing it to stand for 30 minutes. A plot of absorbance values of these solutions against concentration of vanadium showed linear variation.

Experiment on the Study of Interferences: For studying the interference effect of each metal ion in their different mole ratios to vanadium viz. 10 : 1, 1 : 1 and 1 : 10, appropriate volume of the solution of the metal ion under investigation was added separately to each of the three 2 ml of 0.0005M solution of vanadium. The colour in each of these solutions was then developed by the procedure given above and the absorbance was measured at 520 nm. The colour in 2 ml of 0.0005 M vanadium solution in absence of any other metal ions was similarly developed and its absorbance too was measured at 520 nm for comparison.

Determination of vanadium in high speed steel: About a gram of the high speed steel sample (No. 64b), procured from the Bureau of Analysed Samples Ltd., was accurately weighed into a beaker and was dissolved by heating with 10 ml of 1 : 1 HClO_4 and 1 ml of concentrated HNO_3 . Solution was then evaporated to dryness and to the dry mass was added sufficient 1 : 1 HCl to dissolve all soluble matters. The resulting solution along with precipitated tungstic acid was saturated with H_2S in a conical flask, and was subsequently heated on a water bath for complete precipitation of molybdenum. Mixed precipitate was then filtered through No. 40 Whatman filter paper and was washed with H_2S water. The filtrate after boiling off H_2S was made up to 250 ml in a standard flask.

An aliquot (0.5 to 2 ml) of the above solution was taken in a separating funnel and it was made 6N with respect to HCl by adding an equal volume of concentrated HCl. Solution was then shaken for 2-3 minutes with 5 ml of isobutyl methyl ketone. Aqueous layer was transferred to another separating funnel and two more extractions were done with isobutyl methyl ketone to reduce appreciably the concentration of iron in the aqueous layer. To the aqueous layer so obtained was added 1 ml of 5% tartaric acid to prevent interference due to chromium. The colour development and absorbance measurement in this solution was then made as described in the calibration procedure. Experiments were repeated with different aliquots of the same sample solution and also with different weighed samples of high speed steel. An average of a number of such determinations indicated the amount of vanadium present to be 1.93% as against 1.99% actually present.

Discussion

The indirect spectrophotometric method of determination of vanadium is virtually the method of determination of iron using 2,2'-dipyridyl. Vanadium(IV) obtained by the reduction of vanadium(V) with sodium nitrite and concentrated HCl is further oxidised quantitatively by iron(III) producing an equivalent amount of iron(II). Formation of 2,2'-dipyridyl complex with iron(II) which has long been known for colorimetric as well as spectrophotometric determination of iron can, thus, under the above situation provide a means for estimation of vanadium too. The molar absorptivity of ferrous-dipyridyl complex being higher than the BPHA method in the direct determination of vanadium, the method has greater sensitivity [$0.0055 \mu\text{g V cm}^{-3}$ (520 nm)] than the BPHA method [$0.0109 \mu\text{g V cm}^{-3}$ (510 nm)]. Thus in spite of the specificity of BPHA in the determination of vanadium, the present method can give better recovery of vanadium.

In the development of colour of the ferrous-dipyridyl complex, although a pH of 5-8 has been recommended, a slightly acidic pH between 5 and 6 is maintained to avoid precipitation of ferric hydroxide and phosphate, the latter resulting from the sodium phosphate added to mask the colour due to ferric ion.

An examination of the effect of the presence of other metal ions viz. Ca(II), Mg(II), Mn(II), Pd(II) and Pt(IV) revealed that these metal ions when present with vanadium in the mole ratio 10 : 1, 1 : 1 and 1 : 10 did not interfere. Fe(III) added (2 ml of 0.1% FeCl_3 solution) for oxidation of vanadium is in the mole ratio 10 : 1. The presence of iron in the mole ratio to the extent of 12 : 1 vanadium is tolerated. Zn(II) and Ni(II) although did not interfere when present in the mole ratio 1 : 1 and 1 : 10, they did interfere when present in the ratio 10 : 1. Other metal ions viz. Cu(II), Co(II), Cd(II), Cr(III), Mo(VI) and W(VI) interfered even when present in 1 : 10 ratio. Pb(II) in this proportion did not interfere but it did at higher concentrations. The presence of oxalic and citric acid retarded the development of colour of the ferrous dipyridyl complex. However tartaric acid did not have any adverse effect. In presence of Cr(III), precipitation occurred during colour development. Addition of 1 ml of 5% tartaric acid prevented precipitation and at the same time resulted in good recovery of vanadium.

The method has been tested for estimation of vanadium in standard sample of high speed steel and the recovery of vanadium was found to be good with an error within 3%.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their gratitude to Prof.

N. N. Siddhanta for providing laboratory facilities in carrying out this work.

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